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ABSTRACTS

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Rajbaug, Next to Hadapsar, Loni Kalbhor, Pune 412201, India.

+91 744 7444 027 / 28 | +91 914 6051 841 / 42

www.mitbio.edu.in / icrtb@mituniversity.edu.in

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Harnessing the role of Phosphate Solubilizing Bacteria (PSB) from the microbiota of *Azadirachta indica* in formulation of Nanotechnology based Bio-fertilizer

Sunita Fernandes¹ and Priyanka Sharma*¹

^{1,*}*MIT School of Bioengineering Science and Research, MIT Art Design Technology University, Pune, India.*

*Corresponding author: priyanka.sharma@mituniversity.edu.in

Abstract: As the global population expands, the demand for the food also surges. So, modern agriculture is escalating more in the use of agrochemicals to boost crop productivity with global higher food demand. The studies conducted by agriculturists highlighting the negative impacts on indiscriminate use of synthetic agrochemicals viz. nutrient depletion on account of soil degradation, water contamination and imbalance in the ecosystem. Hence, on considering the properties of nanomaterials and biofertilizers (PGPR), researchers are diving towards the development of sustainable and cost-effective nano-biofertilizer to enhance plant traits by minimizing climatic calamities. Nano-fertilizers provide increased nutrient availability, microbial revitalization, resistance to various diseases and reduced nutrient losses that can lead to improved crop health and yield. Since phosphorus is a necessary macronutrient for plant growth and development, PSB are able to convert insoluble forms of phosphate into soluble ones. These bacteria can be Nano-formulated to improve nutrient bioavailability and yield as well. *Azadirachta indica*, often known as Indian Lilac or Neem, has been recognized for its ethanopharmacological properties. This plant system interacts with several microorganisms that have been shown to be advantageous in the fields of bioenergy, medicine, and agrochemicals. Therefore, the present study emphasizes on the encapsulation of PSB by using biopolymers. These nano-polymer enabled bio-fertilizers significantly improve organic nutrient absorption while also retaining shelf life of bacteria to enhance the dynamics of soil-plant interaction as promising for sustainable agriculture.

Keywords: Nanotechnology, bio-fertilizers, phosphate-solubilizing bacteria(PSB), soil plant interaction, sustainable agriculture.